

LOCATION AND ACHIEVEMENTS IN ORAL ENGLISH AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KOGI STATE.

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Abstract

This study investigated school location and students' academic achievements in Secondary Schools in Kogi State. The need for this study was due to the persistent poor achievement of students in Secondary Schools in both internal and external examinations for some years now. The study became imperative with the aim of identifying the factors correlating to poor achievement among students. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study was 11,609 senior secondary schools. Three Students were sampled from all secondary schools in Kogi State. The sample of the study included 375 senior secondary school SSS3 students. This study adopted a correlational survey research design method with the adoption of a multi-stage sampling technique. The research instruments were a researcher-structured questionnaire entitled "School Location and Students' Academic Achievement Questionnaire" (SLASAAQ) and an Oral English Achievement Test (ELAT). The reliability of the instrument was established. The internal consistency of the instruments was assessed using the Cronbach's alpha method for the questionnaire and the Kuder-Richardson formular for the Oral English Language Achievement Test. The items in the questionnaire had a reliability Coefficient of 0.92, while the English Language Achievement Test yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.98. Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient statistical tool was used to answer the research questions, while linear regression was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed a significant relationship between urban schools and students' academic achievement. There is also a significant relationship between rural schools and students' academic achievement. It was also recommended among others that a state-wide survey of schools should be undertaken by the Secondary Education Board to determine which schools are deficient in what resources and which resources should be equalized and that materials that will make the teaching and learning process run smoothly should be provided at rural schools.

Introduction:

Students' academic achievements have always been of special interest to parents, educational stakeholders, and the society at large. The primary concern of any educator who is entrusted with the responsibility of selecting

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students for any advance training program in a given field is the ability to estimate as accurately and as early as possible the probability that a candidate will succeed or fail. Globally, poor student academic performance has been a major concern for major stakeholders in education. In most European countries, academic performance remains low, especially among senior secondary schools (European Union Monitoring Report, 2013).

The persistent occurrence of poor external examination results among Nigerian students, especially those in secondary schools, is a matter that has become a source of concern for successive governments and major stakeholders in the education sector in Nigeria today. Many Nigerian students are performing below expectations in their academic careers. Over the years, the majority of students who sit for the May/June West African Examination Council have recorded poor achievement not only in the area of overall performance but also in English.

The academic achievement trend of secondary school students in Nigeria in the last two decades has become a major source of concern for all stakeholders (Nwadinigwe & Azuka-Obieke, 2012). There has been a massive decline in the performance of students in both the National Examination Council and the West African Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (Dawa, Adamu & Olayomi, 2015). To Adesemowo (2005), the annual release of Secondary Certificate Examination Result depicts the problematic nature and generalization of poor secondary school students' performance in different school subjects, especially Mathematics and English Language among secondary school students. The stakeholders in education agreed that the huge investment in education is not yielding the desired dividend.

Poor academic achievement is not only peculiar to Nigeria but also obtainable in other nations of the world. In Pakistan, students' academic achievement has become a serious issue that is mostly discussed among high school teachers, administrators, the education department, and the government (Hayat, Nisar UIHaq, Sajjad, Abbas & Raza, 2018). According to Giunchiglia, Zeni, Gobbi, Bignotti, and Bison (2018), this scenario is a result of students' use of social media and smartphones. They noted that students used social media extensively. In recent times, students' academic performance in WASSCE examinations has declined in Kogi State. The percentage of those who had credits in five subjects including English and Mathematics in the state was at 35.78%, 45.69%, 43.19%, 68.02% and 50.95% in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018, respectively (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020). Abia recorded 59.72%, 69.98%, 82.03%, 76.52% and 82.25% in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018, respectively, to top the list. Anambra recorded 60.62%, 64.99%, 71.85%, 71.53%, and 51.40% in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018, respectively. The percentage of those who had credits in five subjects including English and Mathematics in Enugu State stood at 49.67%, 46.20%, 60.85%, 72.57% and 61.66% in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018, respectively (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

Apart from performing well in subjects in their areas of specialization, students are expected to perform very well in the English Language because it must be passed by every student before gaining admission into tertiary institutions. The importance of the English language as a school subject and in national development has been stressed. Soyinka (2007) and Jason (2010) described the English language as a global lingua franca and major tool for science, events, business, aviation, international trade, journalism, administration, entertainment and diplomacy. Manivannan (2006) noted that the English language is a tool used to establish viewpoints and promote our worldview. Joshi (2013), on his part, noted that the English language helps students perform well in their social lives, build strong relationships, and better understand issues in life. This point to the fact that without the English language, an individual may not properly fit into the world of today. With specific reference to education, English is a language of instruction in the Nigerian educational system. Proficiency in English affects students' performance in all subjects because it is the language of instruction in schools (Cardenas,

2011). Hence, there is a need for students to perform well in English so as to have the opportunity of being offered admission into higher institutions after the completion of their secondary education.

The importance of the English language in economic, political, social, religious, and educational activities cannot be overstated. Hence, anyone who wants to be relevant in the social, political, and economic sectors must reach an appreciable competence level in reading and writing in the English language. The quality of the products of this educational system in Nigeria is poor. This is most evident in the written and spoken skills of English language students. This is clearly displayed in the SSCE WAEC results. The rate at which students perform poorly in English Language is overwhelming.

More so, there is a record of poor English language achievement in secondary schools over the years. This has become a growing problem. The fact that the English Language is the most important subject in the secondary school curriculum is uncontested (Oniha, 2011). The English language is a foundation on which students can effectively understand their teacher in almost all subjects. This means that secondary school students should have a firm grasp of the English language. The student also needs to excel in English because it is one of the core subjects that a student must pass at the credit level in any external examination such as NECO and WAEC before he or she can be granted admission into any tertiary institution. Given the importance of the English language as a subject, common sense dictates that students should perform well in this field. However, the statistics of result performance from NECO revealed that only a fraction of candidates from various Secondary Schools across the country passed the credit level annually (Idowu, 2015). Educational systems, the world over are examination-oriented. Hence, the quality of education could be determined by students' performance in their academic activities like end of the term examinations, end of the year examinations and the WAEC and NECO Examination.

There is persistent poor performance of students in externally written examinations like West African Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination and National Examination Council in general and end-of-term examinations in particular in secondary schools in Kogi State. The problem of poor academic achievement in WAEC has become so great that it has become increasingly difficult for students to pass the number of required subjects for admission into tertiary institutions at once (Yusuf & Adigun, 2010). This situation is of great concern to the government, parents, and guardians. Mass failure in external examinations has been attributed to factors like teachers' qualification, experience, poor salaries and allowances, poor supervision, organizational climate, students' poor ability, unwillingness to learn, and poor peer group influence (Yusuf & Adigun, 2010)

Some factors have been identified as causes of poor academic achievement in students. These factors might include teachers' qualification, experience, poor salaries and allowances, poor supervision, students' unwillingness to learn, and poor peer groups (Ezechi, & Adukwu 2018). Attitudes of students and teachers, study habits, teachers' qualification, teaching methods, school environment, government policy, school location, and family types have been identified in several studies as factors influencing students' academic achievement (Asikhia, 2010 & Akomolafe & Olorumfemi-Olabisi, 2011). Alordiah, Akpadaka, and Oviogbodu (2015) noted that some factors like poor teaching, psychological factors, unpreparedness on the part of the students, poor learning environment, school location, and evaluation process also influence students' academic achievement. Other factors, according to Mhiliwa (2015), that can cause poor achievement of students include lack of support and active participation of parents in the education of learners. He also identified poor management of school resources for effective teaching and learning and the lack of physical facilities as issues with poorly performed schools.

Mwiigi (2014) also stated that many factors account for good or poor academic achievement in secondary

schools, including the quality of students admitted, the type of scholastic materials available in the school and home environment, teaching methods, the nature of administration and teachers' involvement in academic matters. All the aforementioned factors have been noted by scholars as influencing students' academic achievement. However, the study intends to investigate school location and students' time management as correlates of students' academic achievement in Secondary Schools in Kogi State.

Incidentally, School location has been identified by some scholars as a factor affecting school efficiency, including students' achievement. Quirk (2008) defined location as a particular place that is related to other areas. Enyi (2000) previously determined the location status of a School in terms of two urban bias characteristics: administrative status and nature of the occupational activities of a place. School location refers to the location of the school. The site of a school could either be in a rural or urban setting. Rural schools seem to be inferior to urban schools because rural schools lack both human and material resources needed to make teaching and learning extremely effective. Bratte (2010) noted that location affects students' academic achievement. In his study, he noted that students in urban schools performed very well in their academics than their counterparts in rural areas because the infrastructure facilities in urban areas tend to pull the elite of society to such areas. These elites also usually employ private teachers to care for their children after school hours. Students' academic behavior might be influenced not only by the motivating forces of their homes, scholastic ability and academic values but also by the social pressure applied by the participants in the school setting.

It is argued that the reason urban students perform well in academics than rural students might be because they do attract some amenities like pipe borne water, electricity, good roads, and well-equipped schools. The reason might also be that rural schools lack adequate educational facilities for effective teaching and learning. In the same vein, Mofon (2001) stressed that many rural schools are in a dire state of despair and lack basic learning facilities for effective teaching and learning. Poor environments and infrastructural facilities may contribute immensely to poor academic performance. Agu (2017) stated that the disparity in urban and rural secondary schools in terms of educational facilities and teachers' qualities might significantly determine the academic fortunes of students in both locations. Urban locations are characterized by social amenities, high population density, and industrial activity. On the contrary, a rural setting is characterized by an absence of social amenities, low population density, a road network, an income rate, and industrial activities. Ezeudu (2003) stated that school location refers to the urban or rural areas where schools are located. Akpan (2008) indicated that schools in urban areas have an electricity supply, water supply, more teachers, more learning facilities, and adequate infrastructure.

Given the foregoing and given the rather complex and persistent nature of poor academic achievement in schools across gender, there is a need for more micro/level investigation to identify various factors correlated with this problem. In summary, it is the intention of the researchers to examine how school location correlates with students' academic achievement in Secondary Schools in Kogi State.

Statement of the Problem

The achievement of Secondary School students in external examinations has not been encouraging. Students are expected to have a minimum of five credits in the required subjects in their areas of specialization, including English Language and Mathematics, as compulsory subjects to be adjudged successful in the examination. Secondary Schools in Kogi State appear to have an adequate number of teachers, well-qualified teachers and an efficient supervisory system. Despite these, students' performances in internal and external examinations results were not encouraging. The percentage of students with credits in five subjects, including English Language and Mathematics, stood at 35.78%, 45.69%, 43.19%, 68.02%, and 50.95% in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018,

respectively (National Bureau of Statistics 2020).

School location and time management have been identified as factors that can influence students' secondary academic achievement. Previous studies on the influence of these variables on students' academic achievement are not conclusive. While some studies found that there is a significant influence of these variables on students' academic performance, others found that these variables do not significantly influence students' academic achievement. Again given persistent students' poor academic achievements, it may be argued that this may be due to their inability to identify various correlating factors, hence the call by many researchers for more intensive research. This informed the need for the current study. Accordingly, the researcher wants to investigate School location as a correlate of students' academic achievement in Secondary Schools in Kogi State.

Purpose of the Study

This study explored school location as a correlate of academic achievement in Secondary Schools in Kogi State. Specifically, the study sought to find out:

1. The relationship between urban schools and students' oral English achievement in secondary schools in Kogi State.
2. Relationship between rural schools and students' oral English achievement in secondary schools in Kogi State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the relationship between urban schools and students' oral English achievement in secondary schools in Kogi State?
2. What is the relationship between rural schools and students' oral English achievement in secondary schools in Kogi State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at a significance level of 0.05.

1. There is no significant relationship between urban schools and students' academic achievement in oral English in Secondary Schools in Kogi State.
2. There is no significant relationship between rural schools and students' oral English achievement in secondary schools in Kogi State.

Literature Review

Oral English, also known as spoken English, is the form of English used when people speak to one another. This is how the English language is transmitted through a conventional system of sounds. Students learning English as a second language may experience difficulties in Oral English because of the phonological differences between the English language and their mother tongue (Otagburuagu, Obah, Onuigbo & Okorji, 2007).

Traditionally, literacy has been a significant indicator of an educated mind. The educated man was cherished because of the knowledge and social prominence that learning and literacy gave. Because social and economic prominence associated with literacy was usually obtained through education and because educated men were only those who could read and write, much attention was paid to the written form of language. To many learners of English, therefore, what was important was their ability to read and write English very well. However, recent studies in linguistics have led to the re-evaluation of the relationship between spoken and written forms of language. Emphasis has now shifted to communicative competence, which includes grammatical, discourse, sociolinguistic, and strategic competences (Izuagba, 2005). The spoken form of English

is now attracting as much attention as other forms of the language.

Writing on the importance of Oral English, Eyisi (2002) stated that oral English equips one with the ability to understand English speakers, whether they are Nigerians, British, Canadians, or Americans. Competence in Oral English is a significant asset to anyone who wishes to become relevant in the mainstream of international affairs. This is more so in Nigeria, where there is a need for communication between speakers of over four hundred mutually unintelligible languages. Gimson (2004) stated that the essence of the spoken component of the English language is to equip one with the ability to understand educated speakers of English and to be understood by others. Gimson stresses that unless a learner expects to deal with English only in written form, they cannot escape from the acquisition of at least the rudimentary elements of English pronunciation. The purpose of Oral English teaching and learning is therefore to ensure that students reach a level of communication fluency in the use of English so that they can easily pass information in speech and readily retrieve the same from speakers without loss of mutual intelligibility.

Oral English is so important that examination councils in Nigeria have made it a compulsory part of the English language examination. Idowu, Sogbesan, Adofu, Burgess & Burgess (2003: 139) comment that “The importance of speech to a learner of language has necessitated the inclusion of spoken English in the Senior Secondary School Examination. Oral English is compulsory and contributes to the overall marks earned in the examination.” The essence of making Oral English compulsory in the SSCE is to impart to the students the ability to understand English and be understood by competent speakers of English within and outside Nigeria. Oral English needs to be taught properly using innovative techniques.

In Nigeria, schools are located in both urban and rural areas. The location of a school is an important factor in learning, and over the years, there have been controversies on the question of whether school environments have influence on the behavior and attainment of children who attend schools. According to Uzoegwu (2010), the location of a school determines many important aspects of learning, such as learning facilities, environmental factors, infrastructure, number and quality of teachers, and class size. Adequate provision or lack of these facilities may improve or hamper student learning. These factors may also affect students’ language learning achievement. The location of a school can therefore influence a child’s knowledge of Oral English and his or her general knowledge and attitude toward language learning.

A location is a geographical area that is related to other areas. A location is a particular place in relation to other areas (Quirk, 2008). Obiahu (2019) defined location as a particular place or position that is particularly related to other areas. This location can be seen in two ways: urban and rural. In other words, it can also be viewed as a place or area where one spends time or does something. However, the location of a school may have a positive or negative influence on students’ academic achievements. School location can be defined as the location where a school is located, which can be an urban or rural area. According to Akpan (2008), schools in urban areas have an electricity supply, water supply, more teachers, and more learning facilities and infrastructure. Urban areas are those areas with high population density, while rural areas are those with low population, subsistence mode of life, poor amenities like roads, electricity, and water. Rural areas are characterized by lack of infrastructures, aging population and an agrarian orientation. There is a lack of social amenities such as good roads, electricity, and water supply in rural areas. The schools located there are mostly deprived of what it takes to make teaching and learning effective. There are dilapidated school buildings, inadequate learning materials, no libraries, and no laboratories, and even when they are available, they are inadequately equipped. In most cases, teachers in rural schools are usually not very qualified because most qualified teachers normally work their way back to urban areas even after being transferred (Ezeudu, 2003).

In his own submission, Osalusi (2009) observed that there is a perception that rural dwellers are slow-witted hillbillies with little education and an uninformed view of what goes on in the “real world” whereas, those living in urban areas are more exposed to modern technology that can aid learning than those living in rural areas. Howley (2003) asserted that several studies have found significant differences between students in rural and urban schools. In the studies, it was also observed that students living in rural areas of the United States exhibit lower educational performance and a higher likelihood of dropping out of school than their counterparts in urban areas.

Adding his voice on the influence of school location on students’ achievement, Ajayi (2009) noted a significant difference in the academic achievements of students in urban and rural schools. He argued that the better performance of urban students could be attributed to the availability of qualified teachers, a good learning environment, and the provision of facilities in urban schools, which in most cases are conspicuously absent in rural schools. In their submission, Owoye et al (2011) noted that the provision of education in rural areas is normally fraught with difficulties and problems; qualified teachers refuse appointments in isolated villages; villagers refuse to send their children to schools because they are dependent on them for help; parents hesitate to entrust their daughters to male teachers; a lack of roads or satisfactory means of communication makes it difficult to get books and teaching materials to schools.

Academic achievement is defined as the outcome of education. The extent to which a student, teacher, or institution has achieved their educational goals. Wenling (2000) asserted that academic achievement refers to the performance of individuals’ objectives in relation to various types of knowledge and skills. Academic achievement, in other words, has to do with what a student can achieve by execution of class work in the school. Academic achievement, according to Stiggings (2001), is something learners do or achieve at school, college, or university, in class, in a laboratory, or in fieldwork. Adediwura (2007) saw academic achievement as defined by tests and examination scores or marks assigned by subject teachers. It can also be said to be any expression used to represent students’ scholastic standing.

Academic achievement, according to Kyoshaba (2009), is being characterized by achievements on tests associated with coursework and the achievements of students on other types of examinations. Hence, in relation to educational research, the academic achievement of students refers to the observable and measurable behavior of a student in particular studies. For instance, the academic achievement of a student in English includes the observable and measureable behavior of the student at any time during a course. In English, students’ academic achievement consists of their score at any particular time obtained from a test by a teacher. Academic achievement of students consists of scores obtained from teacher-made tests, first term examination, end of session examinations, and internal or external examinations.

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on the Pickle Jar theory developed by Jeremy Wright in 2002. This theory states that the activities and responsibilities of people must be balanced using an effective time management system. This theory emphasizes the appropriate allocation of time for everything. The theory also states that individuals prioritize many aspects of life, such as studying leisure, sleep, and rest. According to the theory, none of these tasks is bad; however, the most important task is efficient management of time. The theory emphasizes individuals starting their day with big and important tasks, followed by smaller tasks and finally finishing small, unimportant tasks. By doing so, one can fit in with everything one should do. The theory is anchored on ‘important things’. To achieve these important tasks, one must minimize distractions. There is a need to prioritize tasks, focus on the most important tasks, and still give room for rest and relaxation. When this is accomplished, one will effectively use one’s time and complete one’s tasks on time with little stress.

The Pickle Jar theory is related to this study because; it emphasizes prioritizing and scheduling tasks in such a

way that important tasks are performed first before less important ones are handled.

Students are expected to prioritize and allocate time appropriately to their tasks to use their time effectively. When students use their study very well through appropriate allocation of time, this may have a reasonable effect on their academic achievement.

Methodology

The researcher adopted a correlational survey design. A correlational survey design is aimed at determining the possibility and degree of relationship that exists between two or more variables. Uzoagulu (2011) stated that correlational design measures the relationship between two variables, that is, the extent of the relationship that exists between two variables, which emphasizes that when the value of one variable increases, the value of the other variable increases likewise. The study area covered the Kogi State of Nigeria. The State was created on the 27th August, 1991, with its capital in Lokoja. It is situated in the North-Central geo-political zone of the country. There are three senatorial zones in the state: Kogi East, Kogi West, and Kogi Central. The population of the study comprised 11,609 senior secondary school and two students from the rural and urban secondary schools in Kogi State as of the 2020/23 academic session. The study was composed of 5482 males and 6127 females (kogi State Ministry of Education, 2021). The sample for this study consisted of 387 students sampled from the population using Taro Yamene's standard sampling procedure. The instruments for collecting data for the study were a researcher-structured questionnaire entitled the "School Location and Students' Academic Achievement Questionnaire" (SLSAAQ) and the Oral English Achievement Test (OEAT). The instruments for this study, which included items from the Oral English Achievement Test (OEAT), were validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Kogi State. The reliability of the instrument was established. The internal consistency of the instruments was assessed using the Cronbach's alpha method for the questionnaire and the Kuder-Richardson formular for the English Language Achievement Test. The items questionnaire yielded a reliability Coefficient of 0.92, while the English Language Achievement Test yielded 0.98. In answering the research questions, Pearson's product moment correlation was used. The decision rule was that any coefficient between 0.80 and 1 was described as having a very high or near perfect positive correlation, while any coefficient between 0.60 and 0.80 was described as having a high positive relationship. The coefficient between 0.40 and 0.60 is described as a medium positive relationship. After applying the linear regression tool, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis when the P value was less than the alpha value and did not reject the null hypothesis when the P value was greater than the alpha value.

Result

Research Question 1:

What is the relationship between urban schools and students' Oral English achievement in secondary schools in Kogi State?

Table1: Correlation coefficients of urban schools and students' achievement levels

Urban location and urban achievement			
Urban Location	1.0000		.8797
		(181)	(181)
	P=.		P=.000
Urban Achievement	.8797		1.0000
		(181)	(181)
	P=.000		P=.
	r=0.88		r²=0.77

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2024.

The results in Table 1 show a correlation coefficient(r) of 0.88, which indicates a very strong relationship. This indicates that there is a very strong relationship between urban schools and students' achievement in Oral English in Secondary Schools in Kogi State.

However, the coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.77, which is 77% when converted to percentage. This value

explains the variation in Oral English achievement as explained by students in urban locations.

Research Question 2:

What is the relationship between rural schools and students’ achievement in oral English in Secondary Schools in Kogi State?

Table 2: Correlation coefficients of rural schools and students’ achievement of rural location

	Rural Achievement	
Rural Location (194) P=.	1.0000	.9383 (194) P=.000
Rural Achievement (194) P=.000	.9383	1.0000 (194) P=. r=0.94 r ² =0.88

Source: Researcher’s Fieldwork, 2024.

The results in table 2 show a correlation coefficient of 0.94. This indicates that there is a very strong relationship between rural schools and students’ achievement in Oral English in Secondary Schools in Kogi State. However, the coefficient of determination (r²) was 0.88 or 88%. This value explains the variation in Oral English achievement as explained by students in rural areas.

Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between urban schools and students’ academic achievement in Oral English in Secondary Schools in Kogi State.

Table 3: Significant relationship between urban schools and students’ achievement.

Variable	Computed by r	r-Squared	Adjusted r-squared	Standard error	Beta	t-cal	Sig t
Urban Schools	.87974	.77394	.77267	.81566	.879736	24.755	.0000
Constant						.568	.5704

Source: Researcher’s Fieldwork, 2024.

From Table 3, r represents the coefficient of correlation, which is established on the relationship between urban schools and student achievement. The coefficient of determination (r²) for the computed r value was 0.7739 (77.39%. This value explains students’ opinions on how urban location influences achievement in oral English. On the test of significance of the hypothesis as indicated in table 3, the calculated ‘t’ value is 24.755 while the significance of ‘t’ is 0. 0000.From the two values the null hypothesis (HO₁) which states that the relationship between urban schools and students’ English language achievement scores is not significant, is rejected. Equally, the researcher observed that a P value of 0.0000 was less than an alpha value of 0.05. On the basis of this, the researcher concludes that the relationship between urban schools and students’ achievement scores is significant.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between rural schools and students’ oral English achievement in secondary schools in Kogi State.

Table 4: Significant relationship between rural schools and students' achievement.

Variable	Computed by r (r)	r-Squared	Adjusted r-squared	Standard error	Beta	t-cal	Sig t
Rural Schools	.93831	.88042	.87980	.43010	.938307	37.598	.0000
Constant						3.905	.0000

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2024.

From Table 4, r represents the coefficient of correlation, which is established on the relationship between the two variables. The coefficient of determination (r^2) for the computed value was 0.88042, which is 88.04%. This value explains students' opinions on how urban location influences achievement in English. On the test of significance of the hypothesis as indicated in table 4, the calculated 't' value is 37.598 while the significance of 't' is 0.0000. From these two values, the null hypothesis (H_0), which states that the relationship between rural schools and students' oral English achievement scores is not significant, is rejected. Moreover, a P value of 0.0000 is less than an alpha value of 0.05. This result led the researcher to conclude that the relationship between urban schools and students' achievement scores is significant.

Discussions

The results, as seen in Table 1, reveal that there is a very strong relationship between urban schools and students' oral English achievement. This means that the location of the school determines the achievements of students. The students must have performed well because they had access to good reading materials and qualified teachers. They also have modern books in the library and are provided with instructional materials for the teaching and learning process. The presence of social amenities must have contributed to their oral English achievement.

This finding agrees with Owoeye, Yara, and Onah (2011), who noted that students' achievements are determined by where a school is located. The finding is also in line with that of Adesegun, Dada and Adu(2016), who reported that students whose schools are located in Government Reserved Ares and Housing Estates have higher academic achievement than those whose schools are located near noisy places. Chianson (2014) also agreed that student achievement has a relationship with the location of their schools. He reported that urban schools have better achievements than rural schools. The findings of Umar and Samuel (2018) are also in accordance with this finding. They found that there existed a relationship between urban schools and students' achievement in Basic Science among Junior Secondary School students. This finding also agreed with Ellah and Itah (2017), who reported that urban students performed better than rural students. This finding contradicts those of Ezeudu (2003), Kissau (2006) and Bosede (2010), who noted that students' achievements are not determined by the location of the school.

The results in Table 2 reveal a very strong relationship between rural schools and students' oral English achievement. The p value of 0.0000 is less than the significance level of 0.05. This indicates a significant relationship between the two variables under examination. Although they lack adequate qualified teachers, instructional materials, and good physical facilities that enable the teaching and learning process to run smoothly, rural students still recorded good performances more than urban schools. This may be a result of self-motivation by students to work hard to do well in their academics. Hence, whether a student finds himself or herself in urban or rural schools, the students' determination to succeed matters. The findings of this study are in agreement with Bosede (2010) and Ugwuanyi (2012), who affirmed that students' achievements are not determined by the location of the school. It is also in line with Essien (2017), who reported that rural schools performed better than urban schools. This indicates that there is a relationship between rural schools and student achievement.

Conclusion

The study focused mainly on school location as a correlate of students' academic achievement in Oral English in Secondary Schools in Kogi State. Based on the findings and discussions, the following conclusions were made: There was a very high positive relationship between urban schools and students' oral English achievement. A significant relationship between urban schools and students' achievement in Oral English in Secondary Schools in Kogi State was also observed from the test of hypothesis. There was a near perfect (very high positive) relationship between rural schools and students' achievement in Oral English in Secondary Schools in Kogi State. From the result of the hypothesis, a significant relationship was found between rural schools and students' achievement in oral English in Secondary Schools in Kogi State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study.

1. The government should not relent in providing the necessary instructional materials and other facilities that will continue to enhance students' achievement in urban schools. A state-wide survey of schools should be undertaken by the Secondary Education Board to determine which schools are deficient in resources and which resources should be equalized.
2. Rural school students should be encouraged to use the available resources at their disposal to enhance their performance in both internal and external examinations. Governments at all levels should improve the provision of the necessary resources to enhance the performance of students in rural areas. There should also be an even distribution of resources to urban and rural schools.
3. That quiz competition for schools on oral English will be conducted quarterly, and awards and rewards will be given to successful learners for both urban and rural schools. This will pose challenges for weak and uninterested students or learners of oral English

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